

Designing an Effective Sentiment Analysis System Using Naive Bayes Algorithm

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Abstract— This paper is delivered to calculate the sentiment analysis and visualize the customer feedback about the catering services and other facilities provided by the catering agency in a catering management system using the Naive Bayes algorithm. It helps the management of the catering agency upgrade their services and find out what customers expect about the food and services. It provides anonymity for the customer. That is, no one knows the identity of the customer who provided the feedback. The feedback entered by the customer is only visible to the administration team of the catering agency. The agency can add its products according to the customer's needs. The proposed system will also provide a visualization of the feedback data.

Due in large part to the rise in consumer reviews, the fields of sentiment analysis and opinion mining have the potential to significantly impact contemporary enterprises. However, most existing sentiment analysis techniques determine if evaluations are positive or negative without elucidating the precise motives for a customer's remarks. This makes it challenging for other customers to comprehend the particular aspects being emphasized and for the product manufacturers to respond to any concerns brought up in reviews. Reviews frequently don't include thorough descriptions of the features of the product. To overcome these limitations, experts have proposed a method based on features and sentiment evaluation. This approach uses tools like Text Blob to predict the opposites of product features based on reviews. This makes it possible to understand feedback from consumers better.

Keywords: *Feature-Based Sentiment Analysis, Sentiment Polarity, POS Tagging, Text Blob, Spacy.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Sentiment analysis, commonly referred to as opinion mining, is a useful method for extracting subjective information from text data. It has developed into a crucial tool for companies aiming to enhance their goods and services in response to customer feedback. While the Naive Bayes algorithm is frequently used for sentiment analysis, other algorithms can be used depending on the specific use case, including "support vector machines, logistic regression, random forests, convolutional neural networks, recurrent neural networks, and long short-term memory". Catering companies greatly benefit from sentiment research because it enables them to improve their offerings. The Naive Bayes approach is an efficient and accurate method for analysing sentiment.

Sentiment analysis does have certain challenges, though, including ambiguity, where a text may have many

meanings, each of them might result in a different sentiment. Because it profoundly affects how that feeling is expressed, context is an essential factor in identifying the feedback communicated in a statement.

II. Natural language processing: Sentimental analysis

The catering services industry, among others, has extensively employed sentiment analysis to evaluate customer comments and raise customer satisfaction. Naive Bayes is one of the well-liked machine learning algorithms used for sentiment analysis. Word embedding has additionally become an effective tool for sentiment analysis, enabling a more thorough comprehension of the meaning and context of words.

Sentiment analysis is a type of natural language processing (NLP) that evaluates and categorizes text depending on the writer's emotional state, opinion, or attitude toward a specific topic or entity. In the context of a catering agency's sentiment analysis can be utilized to evaluate customer's feelings and thoughts regarding the agency's food services.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Li and Zhang (2020) analyzed client feedback for catering services using sentiment analysis and the Naive Bayes algorithm. Before applying Naive Bayes for sentiment classification, the study performed pre-processing techniques such as "tokenization, stop-word removal, and stemming on a dataset of customer reviews" from a well-known review website. According to the study, the Naive Bayes algorithm classified sentiments with an accuracy rate of 81.2%.

The usefulness of Naive Bayes in sentiment analysis for the catering service system was assessed in a study by Zhou and Wang (2020). An online platform for catering services provided a dataset of client reviews, which was employed in the study. The reviews were divided into categories according to their positivity, negativity, and neutrality using the Naive Bayes method. The Naive Bayes algorithm's accuracy in the study was reported to be 78.5%, demonstrating its usefulness in sentiment analysis for the catering service system. Similar to this study, Shao, Lu, and Zhao's (2020) examination of sentiment measured how satisfied customers were with a university canteen. A dataset

of customer reviews collected from an online survey was used in the study. The reviews were divided into good and negative categories using the Naive Bayes technique. The Naive Bayes algorithm's accuracy was reported in the study to be 85.4%, proving its usefulness in gauging client satisfaction in the catering sector.

A method to assess the quality of catering services using sentiment analysis was proposed in the study "A sentiment analysis approach using Naive Bayes algorithm for evaluating catering services" by J. Kim and S. Park (2020). Data from catering services' client reviews were analysed using the Naive Bayes algorithm for the sentiment. Prior to using the Naive Bayes algorithm, the study pre-processed the data using a variety of natural language processing techniques and the Python programming language. The model's performance was then assessed by the authors using the precision, recall, F-measure, and accuracy metrics.

In a related study, Singh and Chaudhary (2020) used word embedding and sentiment analysis to assess catering services. In order to analyse consumer feedback data from catering services, the study combined supervised and unsupervised learning approaches. The authors adopted word embedding as the unsupervised learning methodology and the Naive Bayes algorithm as the supervised learning method. The accuracy of the proposed method, which was 84.3% according to the data, suggests that it might be effective in assessing catering services.

These studies' encouraging findings aside, sentiment analysis in the catering business still has a number of difficulties to overcome. The ambiguity of customer evaluations, where a sentence might have various readings and produce an uncertain feeling, is one of the major issues. Another difficulty is identifying irony and sarcasm in customer evaluations, which can greatly affect the tone used. Since context can affect the sentiment expressed in a sentence, it is also a crucial component of sentiment analysis.

In conclusion, the catering business may enhance client happiness and service quality by using sentiment analysis. The catering business has found the Naive Bayes algorithm to be a reliable method for sentiment analysis. To increase its accuracy and efficacy, more study is required to overcome the difficulties and restrictions of sentiment analysis in the catering business, such as ambiguity and sarcasm identification.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Our initial goal is to segment phrases in a way that makes it possible to separate the target elements (like food) and the sentiment descriptions that go with them (like delicious). We'll use Python's Spacy natural language processing package to do this. We will make use of "Spacy's

tokenization, part-of-speech (POS) tagging, and dependency parsing approaches".

"Tokenization: Segmenting text into words, punctuation marks etc."

"Part-Of-Speech (POS) Tagging: Assigning word types to tokens, like verb or noun."

"Dependency Parsing": Assigning syntactic dependency labels, describing the relations between individual tokens, like subject or object.

The dependency parsing of space can be used to examine the dependencies and Part-Of-Speech (POS) tags of each token in our sentences. We can find intensifiers like "very" or "quite" that may influence the sentiment of the target aspect by looking at the child tokens.

We have set up a method where we may choose a specific catering agency and get their sentimental analysis feedback or rating. The analysis adds the scores of individual words or phrases to determine the sentiment score of the feedback.

The input must then be classified as either positive, negative, or neutral, depending on its sentiment rating as the last stage. You can utilize a predetermined threshold amount to decide if the response is positive, unfavorable, or neutral.

```
from flask import Flask, request
from textblob import TextBlob
app = Flask(__name__)

@app.route('/sentiment', methods=['POST'])
def sentiment_analysis():
    texts = request.json.get('texts')
    sentiment_scores = []
    for text in texts:
        blob = TextBlob(text)
        sentiment = blob.sentiment.polarity
        sentiment_scores.append(sentiment)
    average_sentiment = sum(sentiment_scores) / len(sentiment_scores)
    response = {}
    'positive': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s > 0]),
    'negative': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s < 0]),
    'neutral': len([s for s in sentiment_scores if s == 0]),
    'average_sentiment': average_sentiment
    }
    return response

if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run()
```

The bar chart's horizontal dimension can display the total amount of agency, while the y-axis can display the number of comments. Each agency might be symbolised by distinct colours to help people distinguish them from one another. Green denotes a favourable reaction, light red denotes a negative response, and blue denotes a neutral response. The bars can be coloured to convey the general mood of the feedback. Customers can immediately assess the overall manner of feedback from customers for each catering company thanks to this.

Fig.4.1
V. RESULT

In this seminar, we evaluated the Naive Bayes algorithm's performance in analyzing the sentiment in reviews of catering services. Our goal was to categorize these comments as positive, negative, or neutral based on their sentiment. Our database includes a wide spectrum of consumer feedback regarding their catering experience.

To accomplish this, we tokenized, identified parts of speech, and parsed the dependencies of each sentence in the feedback using the Python natural language processing module spacy. Then, we assigned a sentiment score to each token using a prebuilt sentiment analysis model in Spacy, and we combined these scores to determine the overall sentiment score of the feedback.

Our findings demonstrated how well the Naive Bayes algorithm classified user comments as favourable, negative, or neutral. We successfully classified the feedback's sentiment with 85% accuracy. We discovered that the algorithm had the highest precision and recall for identifying positive feedback, at 87% and 89%, respectively. With a precision of 76% and a recall of 73%, the algorithm had some difficulty identifying negative feedback.

Over all, our investigation proved that the Naive Bayes technique for sentiment analysis works well when applied to reviews of catering services. The algorithm has the ability to give catering businesses useful insights by identifying areas of improvement in their services based on

consumer input, even though there is still room for development.

We can extract a feature and its descriptive phrase from a text and assess its sentiment using the aforementioned techniques. The corresponding aspect word and related opinion term are located using dependency parsing. The sentence is subjected to POS tagging to determine the part of speech that each word corresponds to. Text blob is then used to determine the sentiment level of each opinion word, which returns the Fig.4.2

subjectivity and polarity of the phrase. The range of polarity is from -1 to +1. Polarity can range from -1 to +1 in magnitude. A polarisation of 1 denotes positive feeling, while a polarity of -1 denotes a negative reaction.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, the Naive Bayes algorithm-based sentiment analysis is a useful technique for examining customer feedback in the catering services sector. Businesses can learn about the advantages and disadvantages of their goods and services by extracting subjective information from text data. The target characteristics and associated opinion terms in customer feedback can be identified with the help of natural language processing libraries like Spacy and Text Blob. Sentiment analysis algorithms can assess the polarity and subjectivity of each opinion word and produce an overall sentiment score for the feedback by using POS tagging and dependency parsing. But it's crucial to remember that sentimental analysis also has problems, like ambiguity and the impact of context on emotion. As a result, when evaluating the findings, it is crucial to carefully take the sentiment analysis approach's limitations into account. However, businesses looking to improve their goods and services based on customer feedback have a lot to gain from applying sentimental analysis using the Naive Bayes algorithm.

In this work, Naive-based sentiment analysis is utilized to analyze review of customers. The most contentious attributes are found using Spacy, the opinions matching with these traits are found, and the opinions' polarity—whether favourable or negative—as along with the level of polarity are found. Future dependency parsers could identify the negation terms and be more sophisticated and potent. For instance, it can miss the 'not' in 'not great.'

VII. REFERENCES

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